

ISSUES OF SPEECH DEVELOPMENT OF THE CHILD IN PREPARATION FOR SCHOOLING

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Abstract: *In this article, the conflicts that arise during adolescence, the factors of their occurrence, the interests, needs, views, etc. between the parties in interpersonal relations. Problems such as the origin of conflicts and the emergence of conflicts based on these conflicts, as well as social empowerment and social empowerment are highlighted.*

Keywords: *upbringing, training, development, formation, socialization, preschool education, sources of preschool pedagogy, subject of preschool pedagogy, object of preschool pedagogy.*

Аннотация: *Готовность или неготовность ребенка к обучению в школе во многом определяется уровнем его речевого развития. Чем лучше у него будет развита речь до поступления в школу, тем быстрее он овладеет чтением и письмом. Освоение ребёнком навыков и знаний не является достаточным условием и критерием его подготовленности к школе.*

Ключевые слова: *речь ребёнка, воспитание, обучение, развитие, формирование, социализация, дошкольное образование, источники дошкольной педагогики, предмет дошкольной педагогики, объект дошкольной педагогики.*

The readiness or unpreparedness of a child for schooling is largely determined by the level of his speech development. The better his speech will be developed before entering school, the faster he will master reading and writing. Mastering skills and knowledge by a child is not a sufficient condition and criterion for his readiness for school. In addition to knowing numbers and letters, there is

something more important that parents sometimes miss in their work of preparing children for school. This is the oral speech of the child, the development of which is a necessary condition for the successful assimilation of written speech (reading). A future student should have a sufficient vocabulary, be able to correctly and logically express thoughts, memorize and read poetry, and also retell short texts. The degree of richness and grammatical correctness of the child's oral speech depends on his understanding of what he read. In other words, each child must have a sufficient level of development of coherent oral speech and thinking by the beginning of classes in the first grade of the school.

Not all parents understand the importance of the development of children's speech. Some believe that their children are already the smartest, some believe that they do not have the strength for this, many think that the kindergarten will do everything for them anyway. Most parents pay little attention to the development of speech in a child. Here are some of the answers of parents: "We read in syllables", "We write", "We count". Based on these results, we can conclude that parents do not understand what methods and methods need to develop the speech of their child. There are, of course, other answers: "We compose stories from pictures", "We develop fine motor skills", "We read books", "We come up with riddles", "We talk about the world around us". But these are the answers of those mothers who are teachers themselves, or who already have older children.

In order to speed up and facilitate the process of mastering the necessary skills by the child, it is necessary to combine three equally important and mutually related components in your work on preparing the child - communication with the child, playing with him and his education. In order for a child to simultaneously enjoy such games and successfully master the skills necessary for his development, neither a special room nor absolute silence is needed. All this can be done with the same, if not greater, success in a free and completely relaxed environment. Extremely necessary for the development of the child are various children's games, drawing, modeling and other types of children's creativity.

To teach 6-year-old children the skills of oral speech, as a necessary condition for the development of reading (writing) skills, I offer some educational games and guidelines:

Games that develop the child's oral speech:

Vocabulary replenishment

game "One-many" (name objects in the singular and plural, in the genitive case of the plural)

The development of the grammatical structure of speech

"Greedy" (call each item yours: mine, mine, mine, mine)

"Count" (count items one by one, two by five)

"Hide and Seek" (alternately close objects and say what is not)

"Rulers" (walking fingers along the words-rulers, make a sentence)

"Make up a story"(make a story according to the scheme or supporting questions)

"" (coherently tell what is wrong)

Nonsense Answer orally, correctly building the statement

Recommendations for parents on the development of oral speech of the child:

* Pay attention to how coherent, logical and grammatically correct the child expresses his thoughts.

* Help the child describe objects, events. At the same time, the boundaries of the child's knowledge expand and his speech is enriched.

* When learning poems and songs, the child should not create the appearance of "as if singing", not understanding the meaning of words and pronouncing inarticulate syllables. It is necessary to help him, especially in songs, to correctly understand and pronounce every word. Therefore, sing along with him.

* Teach your child to find and invent rhymes.

* Use yourself more often and encourage the use of sayings, proverbs and common expressions by children.

* Teach your child to invent and make riddles.

* Learn to come up with funny stories.

The most significant changes in the system of interaction between the family and the preschool institution occurred in the 1990s. This is due to the education reform, which could not but affect the system of preschool education, which led to the acceptance of the positive role of the family in the process of raising children and the need to interact with it.

Currently, the system of preschool education is being restructured, now the center of this system is the humanization and de-ideologization of the pedagogical process, the goal of which is now not raising the child as a member of society, but the free development of the individual.

In connection with the foregoing, I would like to pay attention to modern methods and forms of interaction between the family and the preschool educational institution in the preparation of children for school.

The interaction of the preschool institution and the family at the stage of preparing children for school is one of the most important areas of work in the preschool educational institution.

Most parents have a misconception that a child's readiness for schooling is made up of a number of skills, such as: reading, counting, writing. But the main task of the educator is to convey to the parents that interest in the school can be successfully formed even in the absence of these skills. Such skills characterize the transition from preschool to primary school age. Parents are not always familiar with such components of the child's readiness for educational activities, therefore, the teacher of the preparatory group for school needs to inform parents about such age-related features.

Kindergarten teachers are encouraged to carry out a number of activities, which, as a rule, include consultations for parents, drawer folders, parent-teacher meetings. The topics of these parent meetings and consultations are quite diverse, but they necessarily include information about working with parents in the process of preparing children for school, which in turn can provide them with pedagogical and psychological assistance.

The successful formation of these qualities is reflected in a steady desire to acquire knowledge and skills, to make a sufficient amount of effort for this.

Work with parents is carried out in several standard areas: the provision by employees of the preschool educational institution of the necessary assistance to the family in matters of raising a child; inclusion of all family members in the educational process; cultural and educational work with parents; joint work with parents to create conditions for the realization of the creative potential of the child.

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